

LINEAR GEOMETRY: CLASSICAL INCIDENCE PROPERTIES

TARAS BANAKH, IVAN HETMAN, ALEX ILCHUK, VLAD PSHYK, OKSANA SKYHAR

ABSTRACT. Linear Geometry describes geometric properties that depend on the notion of a line. The fundamental structure studied in Linear Geometry is the structure of a liner. It is a set of points endowed with a family of subsets called lines. This family should satisfy two axioms, one of which is the first Euclid axiom postulating that any distinct points belong to a unique line. In this survey paper we discuss liners that satisfy classical incidence conditions named after Desargues, Pappus, Thales, Moufang, Fano, Boole.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is the third survey in the series of surveys that describe the contents of the monograph “Linear Geometry and Algebra” [2]. The first survey [3] concentrated at properties of liners that depend on flat hulls (flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity), the second survey [4] discussed completions and projectivizations of liners. In this survey we study liners that satisfy some classical incidence conditions named after prominent geometers: Desargues, Pappus, Thales, Moufang, Fano. The material of this survey covers Chapters 10, 11, 21, 22, 43, 44, 46 of the book [2].

1. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall the basic notions of Linear Geometry, needed for understanding the main results of this survey.

A *liner* is a set X of *points*, endowed with a family \mathcal{L} of subsets of X called *lines* such that the following two axioms are satisfied:

- any two distinct points belong to a unique line;
- any line contains at least two distinct points.

A liner X is κ -*long* for a cardinal κ if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| \geq \kappa$. A liner X is called *Steiner* if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| = 3$.

Let (X, \mathcal{L}) be a liner. For two distinct points $x, y \in X$ we denote by \overline{xy} the unique line containing those points. If $x = y$, then we put $\overline{xy} := \{x\} = \{y\}$.

A subset $A \subseteq X$ is called *flat* if $\overline{xy} \subseteq A$ for any points $x, y \in A$. For a subset $A \subseteq X$ its *flat hull* \overline{A} is the smallest flat set in X that contains the set A . The *rank* $\|A\|$ of a set $A \subseteq X$ is the smallest cardinality of a subset $B \subseteq X$ such that $A \subseteq \overline{B}$. Flat subsets of rank 3 in a liner are called *planes*.

A liner X is *ranked* (resp. κ -*ranked* for a cardinal number κ) if for any distinct flats $A \subset B$ of finite rank (with $\|B\| \leq \kappa$) we have $\|A\| < \|B\|$. A liner X is called (*weakly*) *modular* if $\|A \cup B\| + \|A \cap B\| = \|A\| + \|B\|$ for any (intersecting) flats A, B in X .

Let κ cardinals. A liner X is defined to be κ -*balanced* if all flats of rank κ have the same cardinality, denoted by $|X|_\kappa$. A liner X is *balanced* if it is κ -balanced for all cardinals κ .

For two flats A, B in a liner X , we say that A is *subparallel* to B and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \subseteq \overline{B \cup \{a\}}$ for all $a \in A$. We say that flats $A, B \subseteq X$ are *parallel* and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \parallel B$ and $B \parallel A$. It is easy to see that two lines L, Λ in a 3-ranked liner are parallel if and only if either $L = \Lambda$ or $L \cap \Lambda = \emptyset$ and $\overline{L \cup \Lambda}$ is a plane.

A bijective map $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two liners (X, \mathcal{L}_X) and (Y, \mathcal{L}_Y) is called a *liner isomorphism* if $\mathcal{L}_Y = \{F[L] : L \in \mathcal{L}_X\}$. An *automorphism* of a liner X is any liner isomorphism

Date: April 7, 2026.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification. 51A05; 51E05.

$F : X \rightarrow X$. The set $\text{Aut}(X)$ of automorphisms of a liner X endowed with the operation of composition is a group, called the *automorphism group* of the liner X .

An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called a

- a *dilation* if every line $L \subseteq X$ is parallel to the line $A[L]$;
- a *translation* if A is a dilation whose fixed-point set $\text{Fix}(A) := \{x \in X : A(x) = x\}$ equals X or \emptyset .

Each subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner (X, \mathcal{L}) carries the line structure

$$\mathcal{L}_A := \{L \cap A : L \in \mathcal{L} \wedge |L \cap A| \geq 2\}$$

turning A into a liner (A, \mathcal{L}_A) , called a *subliner* of the liner (X, \mathcal{L}) .

Definition 1.1. A liner X is called

- *strongly regular* if for every nonempty flat $A \subseteq X$ and point $b \in X \setminus A$, we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \overline{ab}$;
- *regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A, b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \bigcup_{y \in \overline{ob}} \overline{ay}$;
- *weakly regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A, b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \overline{\{o, a, b\}}$.

Next, we recall some Parallellity Postulates and Axioms.

Definition 1.2. A liner X is defined to be

- *Proclus* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists at most one line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$;
- *Bolyai* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists a line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$;
- *Playfair* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists a unique line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$;
- *para-Playfair* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, disjoint lines $L, \Lambda \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists a unique line L_x in X such that $x \in L_x \subseteq P \setminus L$.

The Parallel Postulates are tightly related to the following Parallellity Axioms.

Definition 1.3. A liner X is defined to be

- *projective* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \forall p \in \overline{xy} \forall v \in \overline{oy} \setminus \{p\} (\overline{vp} \cap \overline{ox} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *proaffine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \forall p \in \overline{xy} \setminus \overline{ox} \exists u \in \overline{oy} \forall v \in \overline{oy} \setminus \{u\} (\overline{vp} \cap \overline{ox} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *affine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \forall p \in \overline{xy} \setminus \overline{ox} \exists u \in \overline{oy} \forall v \in \overline{oy} (u = v \Leftrightarrow \overline{vp} \cap \overline{ox} = \emptyset)$;
- *hyperaffine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \forall p \in \overline{xy} \setminus \overline{ox} \exists u \in \overline{oy} (\overline{up} \cap \overline{ox} = \emptyset)$.

By [2, 3.3.17], every affine liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2$ (equal to the cardinality of any line in X) is called the *order* of the affine liner X . By [2, 3.3.24], every 3-long projective liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2 - 1$ is called the *order* of the projective liner X . By [2, 3.4.1], a liner is projective if and only if it is strongly regular.

Definition 1.4. A liner X is called

- an *affine space* if X is 3-long, affine, regular and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$;
- a *projective space* if X is 3-long, projective, and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$.

A *projective completion* of a liner X is any 3-long projective liner Y containing X as a subliner such that $\overline{Y \setminus X} \neq Y$. The set $Y \setminus X$ is called the *horizon* of X in Y . More information on projective completions of liners can be found in Chapter 8 of the monograph [2] and also in the survey [4].

An important example of a projective completion is the spread completion of a completely regular liner. Spread completions of liners are introduced and studied in Chapter 7 of the monograph [2]. Here we briefly recall the definition of the spread completion of a 3-ranked liner.

Let X be a liner and \mathcal{L} be the family of all lines in X . A subfamily $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ is called a *spread of lines* in X if every point $x \in X$ belongs to a unique line $L \in \mathcal{S}$. A line $L \in \mathcal{L}$ is called *spreading* if the family $L_{\parallel} := \{\Lambda \in \mathcal{L} : \Lambda \parallel L\}$ is a spread of lines in X such that $L_{\parallel} = \Lambda_{\parallel}$ for every line $\Lambda \in L_{\parallel}$. In this case, the spread of parallel lines L_{\parallel} is called a *direction* in the liner X . Let \mathcal{S} be the family of all spreading lines in X . The family $\partial X := \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S}\}$ is called the *boundary* of the liner X . So, the boundary of X consists of all directions in X . For a plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, let $\partial\Pi = \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S} \wedge L \subseteq \Pi\}$ be the *boundary* of the plane Π in X . Let \mathcal{P} be the family of planes Π in X such that $|\partial\Pi| \geq 2$.

If the liner X is 3-ranked, then the set $\bar{X} = X \cup \partial X$ endowed with the family of lines

$$\bar{\mathcal{L}} := \{L \cup \{L_{\parallel}\} : L \in \mathcal{S}\} \cup \{\partial\Pi : \Pi \in \mathcal{P}\}$$

is a liner, called the *spread completion* of the liner X . A liner X is called *completely regular* if X is 3-ranked and its spread completion \bar{X} is strongly regular (= projective).

By Corollary 7.6.10 and Theorems 7.6.2 in [2], for every liner we have the implications:

affine regular or strongly regular \Rightarrow completely regular \Rightarrow regular \Rightarrow weakly regular.

A property \mathcal{P} of liners is called a *liner property* if for any isomorphic liners X, Y , the liner X has property \mathcal{P} if and only if Y has property \mathcal{P} .

A property \mathcal{P} of liners is called *complete* if a completely regular liner X has property \mathcal{P} if and only if the spread completion \bar{X} has that property.

There is a simple method of turning a property \mathcal{P} of projective liners in a complete property of an arbitrary liner. Namely, we defined a liner X *completely \mathcal{P}* if X is completely regular and its spread completion \bar{X} has property \mathcal{P} .

Also there are two methods of turning a property of affine liners into a property of projective liners. By [2, 8.3.13], for every hyperplane H in a projective liner Y , the subliner $X := Y \setminus H$ is affine and regular. Let \mathcal{P} be a property of affine liners. A projective liner X is defined to be

- *everywhere \mathcal{P}* if for every hyperplane $H \subset X$, the affine liner $X \setminus H$ has property \mathcal{P} ;
- *somewhere \mathcal{P}* if for some hyperplane $H \subset X$, the affine liner $X \setminus H$ has property \mathcal{P} .

By [2, 7.7.10], a 4-long projective liner X has a complete liner property \mathcal{P} if and only if X is everywhere \mathcal{P} if and only if X is somewhere \mathcal{P} .

2. DESARGUES THEOREMS FOR AFFINE, PROAFFINE, AND PROJECTIVE LINERS

This section contains classical Desargues theorems for affine, proaffine, and projective liners.

Lines L_1, \dots, L_n in a liner are called

- *concurrent* if $\bigcap_{i=1}^n L_i$ is a singleton;
- *parallel* if for any $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ the lines L_i and L_j are parallel;
- *paraconcurrent* if the lines L_1, \dots, L_n are either parallel or concurrent.

Theorem 2.1 ([2, 10.1.1]). *Let A, B, C be paraconcurrent lines in an affine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \geq 4$, and $a, a' \in A \setminus (B \cup C)$, $b, b' \in B \setminus (A \cup C)$, $c, c' \in C \setminus (A \cup B)$ be any points. If $\overline{ab} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$ and $\overline{bc} \parallel \overline{b'c'}$, then $\overline{ac} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$.*

Theorem 2.2 ([2, 10.2.1]). *Let A, B, C be three paraconcurrent lines in a proaffine regular liner X and $a, a' \in A \setminus (B \cup C)$, $b, b' \in B \setminus (A \cup C)$, $c, c' \in C \setminus (A \cup B)$ be distinct points. If $\{a, b, c\}$ and $\{a', b', c'\}$ are two distinct planes, then the set $T := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$ has rank $\|T\| = \{0, 2\}$.*

Definition 2.3. A triple $abc \in X^3$ in a liner X is called a *triangle* if $\|\{a, b, c\}\| = 3$.

Definition 2.4. Two triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in a liner X are called

- *disjoint* if $\{a, b, c\} \cap \{a', b', c'\} = \emptyset$.
- *perspective from a point* $o \in X$ if $\overline{oa} = \overline{oa'}$, $\overline{ob} = \overline{ob'}$ and $\overline{oc} = \overline{oc'}$ are three pairwise distinct lines in X ;
- *centrally perspective* if the triangles $abc, a'b'c'$ are perspective from some point $o \in X$ (called the *perspector* of the triangles $abc, a'b'c'$).

Theorem 2.5 ([2, 10.3.3]). *If abc and $a'b'c'$ are two disjoint centrally perspective triangles in a 3-long projective liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$, then the set $T := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$ has cardinality $|T| = 3$ and rank $\|T\| = 2$.*

3. DESARGUESIAN LINERS

Theorems 2.1, 2.2 and 2.5 motivate the following definition.

Definition 3.1 ([2, 10.4.1]). A liner X is called *Desarguesian* if for every plane $\Pi \subseteq X$ and centrally perspective disjoint triangles $abc, a'b'c'$ in Π , the set

$$T := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$$

has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$.

Theorem 2.2 and Definition 3.1 imply the following useful characterization of Desarguesian Proclus weakly regular liners.

Theorem 3.2 ([2, 10.4.2]). *A Proclus weakly regular liner X is Desarguesian if and only if for every centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X , the set*

$$T := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$$

has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$.

Theorem 3.3 ([2, 10.4.3]). *A Proclus liner X is Desarguesian if and only if every 3-long plane in X is Desarguesian.*

Theorem 3.4 ([2, 10.4.4]). *For every flat H in a Desarguesian projective liner Y , the subliner $X := Y \setminus H$ of Y is Desarguesian.*

Now we consider some important examples of Desarguesian liners.

Theorem 3.5 ([2, 10.4.5]). *Each 3-long proaffine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Desarguesian.*

Theorem 3.6 ([2, 10.4.6]). *Every finite balanced regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Desarguesian.*

Corollary 3.7 ([2, 10.4.8]). *Every affine liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Desarguesian.*

Proposition 3.8 ([2, 10.4.9]). *Every Steiner 3-regular liner X is Desarguesian.*

Example 3.9 ([2, 10.4.10]). The cyclic group \mathbb{Z}_{31} endowed with the family of lines

$$\mathcal{L} := \{L + x : L \in \{\{0, 14, 18\}, \{0, 15, 21\}, \{0, 19, 20\}, \{0, 22, 24\}, \{0, 23, 26\}\}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_{31}\}$$

is a non-Desarguesian Steiner ranked plane: the triangles $abc := (14, 27, 11)$ and $a'b'c' := (18, 13, 30)$ are perspective from the point $o := 0$, but the set $T := (\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'}) \cup (\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'}) \cup (\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'}) = \{10, 17, 19\}$ has rank $\|T\| = 3$.

The following (important and well-known) theorem is a result of combined efforts of Bruck and Ryser [7], Hall [11], [12], and Hall, Swift, Walker [13].

Theorem 3.10. *Every affine or projective liner X of order ≤ 8 is Desarguesian.*

The following theorem is due to Prazmowska [25].

Theorem 3.11 (Prazmowska; [2, 10.5.1]). *An affine liner X is Desarguesian if and only if X satisfies the **Affine Desargues Axiom**:*

(ADA) *for every plane $P \subseteq X$ and centrally perspective triangles $abc, a'b'c'$ in P , if $\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'} = \emptyset = \overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'}$, then $\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'} = \emptyset$.*

4. INVERSE DESARGUES THEOREMS

In this section we shall discuss so-called inverse Desargues Theorems.

Theorem 4.1 ([2, 10.7.1]). *Let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two centrally perspective disjoint triangles in a Desarguesian Proclus plane X . If $\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'} = \emptyset$ and $\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'} = \{x\}$ for some point $x \in X$, then there exists a point $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ such that $\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'} = \{y\}$ and $\overline{x y} \cap \overline{a c} = \emptyset = \overline{x y} \cap \overline{a' c'}$.*

Let us recall that three distinct lines A, B, C are called **paraconcurrent** if they are parallel or $A \cap B \cap C$ is a singleton.

Definition 4.2. Two triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in a liner X are called **paraperspective** if there exist distinct paraconcurrent lines A, B, C in X such that $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$.

Theorem 4.3 ([2, 10.7.4]). *Let X be a proaffine regular liner satisfying the Affine Desargues Axiom and let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles such that the lines $\overline{a a'}, \overline{b b'}, \overline{c c'}$ are distinct. If $\overline{a b} \parallel \overline{a' b'}$, $\overline{b c} \parallel \overline{b' c'}$ and $\overline{a c} \parallel \overline{a' c'}$, then the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are paraperspective.*

Corollary 4.4 ([2, 10.7.5]). *Let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X such that the lines $\overline{a a'}, \overline{b b'}, \overline{c c'}$ are distinct. If $\overline{a b} \parallel \overline{a' b'}$, $\overline{b c} \parallel \overline{b' c'}$ and $\overline{a c} \parallel \overline{a' c'}$, then the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are paraperspective.*

Theorem 4.5 ([2, 10.7.6]). *Let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X such that $\overline{a c} \parallel \overline{a' c'}$ and $\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'} = \{x\}$, $\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'} = \{y\}$ for some points x, y . If $\overline{x y} \parallel \overline{a c}$, then the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are paraperspective.*

Theorem 4.6 ([2, 10.7.7]). *Let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X such that the lines $\overline{a a'}, \overline{b b'}, \overline{c c'}$ are distinct, and $\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'} = \{x\}$, $\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'} = \{y\}$ and $\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'} = \{z\}$ for some points $x, y, z \in X \setminus \{a, a', b, b', c, c'\}$. If the points x, y, z are collinear, then the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are paraperspective.*

5. PARALLEL DESARGUES THEOREMS

In this section we discuss properties of triangles whose vertices lie on three parallel lines in a Desarguesian proaffine liner.

Theorem 5.1 ([2, 10.8.1]). *Let A, B, C be three distinct parallel lines in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X and $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$ are any points. If $\overline{a b} \parallel \overline{a' b'}$ and $\overline{b c} \parallel \overline{b' c'}$, then $\overline{a c} \parallel \overline{a' c'}$.*

Theorem 5.2 ([2, 10.8.2]). *Let A, B, C be three distinct parallel lines in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X and $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$ be any points. If $\overline{ac} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$ and $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \{x\}$ for some point $x \in X$, then there exists a unique point $y \in X$ such that $\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} = \{y\}$ and $\overline{xy} \parallel \overline{ac}$.*

Theorem 5.3 ([2, 10.8.5]). *Let A, B, C be three distinct parallel lines in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X , and let $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, $x, y, z \in X$ be points such that $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \{x\}$, $\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} = \{y\}$, $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \{z\}$. Then the points x, y, z are collinear.*

Theorems 2.2, 5.3 and 4.6 imply the following characterization.

Corollary 5.4 ([2, 10.8.13]). *Let abc and $a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles in a Desarguesian proaffine regular liner X such that the lines $\overline{aa'}$, $\overline{bb'}$, $\overline{cc'}$ are distinct, and $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \{x\}$, $\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} = \{y\}$, $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \{z\}$ for some points $x, y, z \in X \setminus \{a, a', b, b', c, c'\}$. The points x, y, z are collinear if and only if the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are paraperspective.*

6. COMPLETIONS OF DESARGUESIAN PROAFFINE LINERS

Proposition 6.1 ([2, 10.6.7]). *Let Y be a projective completion of a 3-long liner X . If X is Desarguesian, then the horizon $Y \setminus X$ of X in Y is flat and hence the liner X is completely regular.*

Theorem 6.2 ([2, 10.6.15+10.9.1]). *Every Desarguesian regular liner X is completely regular and its spread completion \overline{X} is a Desarguesian projective liner.*

Corollary 6.3 ([2, 10.9.5]). *Any projective completion of a Desarguesian liner is a Desarguesian projective liner.*

Theorem 6.2 implies the following characterization of Desarguesian liners.

Theorem 6.4 ([2, 10.9.6]). *For any liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Desarguesian, proaffine and regular;
- (2) X is completely regular and its spread completion is Desarguesian;
- (3) X is 3-ranked and the spread completion of X is a Desarguesian projective liner.

Let us recall that a liner X is *completely \mathcal{P}* for some property \mathcal{P} of projective liners if X is completely regular and its spread completion \overline{X} has property \mathcal{P} . Theorem 6.4 implies the following corollary.

Corollary 6.5 ([2, 10.9.7]). *A liner is completely Desarguesian if and only if it is Desarguesian, proaffine, and regular.*

Theorem 6.4 implies the following important fact.

Corollary 6.6 ([2, 10.9.8]). *The property of a liner to be Desarguesian is complete.*

Theorem 6.7 ([2, 10.9.9]). *For a projective liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Desarguesian;
- (2) for every flat H in X , the liner $X \setminus H$ is Desarguesian;
- (3) for every hyperplane $H \subset X$, the affine liner $X \setminus H$ is Desarguesian.

If the projective liner X is 3-long, then the conditions (1)–(3) are equivalent to the conditions:

- (4) for some hyperplane H in X , the affine liner $X \setminus H$ is Desarguesian;
- (5) for some flat $H \neq X$, the liner $X \setminus H$ is Desarguesian.

Theorem 6.7 implies the following corollary (which can be also deduced from Corollary 6.6 and Proposition 3.8).

Corollary 6.8 ([2, 10.9.10]). *A (3-long) projective liner X is Desarguesian if and only if X is everywhere Desarguesian (if and) only if X is somewhere Desarguesian.*

A liner X is called *dilation* if for any distinct colinear points $o, x, y \in X$, there exists a dilation $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $A(o) = o$ and $A(x) = y$. We recall that a *dilation* of a liner X is any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ that maps any line $L \subseteq X$ to a parallel line $A[L] \parallel L$.

Theorem 6.9 ([2, 16.8.5]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if X is dilation.*

7. PAPPAN LINERS

Definition 7.1. A liner X is called *Pappian* if for any concurrent lines L, L' in X , and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L', a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, the set $T := (\overline{a'b'} \cap \overline{a'c'}) \cup (\overline{a'c'} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{b'c'} \cap \overline{b'a'})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$.

If the liner X in Definition 7.1 is projective, then the T is not empty. In this case, the Pappianity reduces to the following (more familiar) property.

Proposition 7.2. A projective liner X is Pappian if and only if for every concurrent lines L, L' in \overline{X} , every distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L', a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$ the points $x \in \overline{a'b'} \cap \overline{a'c'}$, $y \in \overline{b'c'} \cap \overline{b'a'}$ and $z \in \overline{a'c'} \cap \overline{a'b'}$ are collinear.

Theorem 7.3 ([2, 21.1.3+21.7.6]). For any projective liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:

- (1) X is Pappian;
- (2) every 4-long plane in X is Pappian;
- (3) for every flat H in X , the liner $X \setminus H$ is Pappian;
- (4) for every hyperplane $H \subset X$, the affine liner $X \setminus H$ is Pappian.

If the projective liner X is 3-long, then the conditions (1)–(4) are equivalent to the conditions:

- (5) for some hyperplane H in X , the affine liner $X \setminus H$ is Pappian;
- (6) for some flat $H \neq X$, the liner $X \setminus H$ is Pappian.

Theorem 7.4 ([2, 21.3.1+21.1.5]). For an affine liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:

- (1) X is Pappian;
- (2) every 4-long plane in X is Pappian;
- (3) for any concurrent lines L, L' in X and any distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$ and $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$ with $\overline{a'b'} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \emptyset = \overline{b'c'} \cap \overline{b'a'}$, we have $\overline{a'c'} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \emptyset$;
- (4) for every concurrent lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$ and $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, if $\overline{a'b'} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$ and $\overline{b'c'} \parallel \overline{b'a'}$, then $\overline{a'c'} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$.

Theorem 7.5 ([2, 21.4.8]). Let L, L' be two coplanar lines in Pappian Proclus liner X and $a, b, c \in L \setminus L', a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$ be distinct points such that $\overline{a'c'} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \emptyset$ and $\overline{a'b'} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \{x\}$ for some point $x \in X$. Then there exists a unique point $y \in X$ such that $\overline{b'c'} \cap \overline{b'a'} = \{y\}$ and $\overline{xy} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \emptyset = \overline{xy} \cap \overline{a'b'}$.

Corollary 7.6. For any lines L, L' in a Pappian Proclus liner X and any points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$ and $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, the conditions $\overline{a'b'} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$ and $\overline{b'c'} \parallel \overline{b'a'}$ imply $\overline{a'c'} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$.

8. THE COMPLETE REGULARITY OF PAPPIAN LINERS

Theorem 8.1 ([2, 21.4.7]). *Every Pappian proaffine regular liner X is completely regular.*

Theorem 8.2 ([2, 21.7.1]). *A completely regular liner X is Pappian if and only if its spread completion \overline{X} is a Pappian projective liner.*

Corollary 8.3 ([2, 21.7.3]). *Any projective completion of a Pappian liner is a Pappian projective liner.*

Corollary 8.4 ([2, 21.7.4]). *A liner is completely Pappian if and only if it is Pappian, proaffine and regular.*

Theorem 8.2 implies the following important fact.

Corollary 8.5 ([2, 21.7.5]). *The property of a liner to be Pappian is complete.*

Corollary 8.6 ([2, 21.7.7]). *A (4-long) projective liner X is Pappian if and only if X is everywhere Pappian (if and only if X is somewhere Pappian).*

For projective and affine regular liners, the following important theorem was proved by Hessenberg [14] in 1905, and completed by Cronheim [6] in 1953 and Pshyk [26] in 2025.

Theorem 8.7 ([2, 21.5.1]). *Every Pappian proaffine regular liner is Desarguesian.*

9. THE DUAL PAPPUS AXIOM

Lines L_1, \dots, L_n in a liner X are called *coplanar* if $\|L_1 \cup \dots \cup L_n\| \leq 3$.

Definition 9.1. A liner X is defined to satisfy the **Dual Pappus Axiom** if for any distinct coplanar lines $A, B, C, A', B', C' \subseteq X$ with $(A \cap B \cap C) \setminus (A' \cup B' \cup C') \neq \emptyset \neq (A' \cap B' \cap C') \setminus (A \cup B \cup C)$, the intersection $(A \cap B') \cup (A' \cap B) \cap (A \cap C') \cup (A' \cap C) \cap (B \cap C') \cup (B' \cap C)$ is not empty.

Theorem 9.2 ([2, 21.8.2]). *A projective liner is Pappian iff it satisfies the Dual Pappus Axiom.*

10. REGULI IN LINERS

Let us recall that two distinct lines L, Λ in a liner X are *skew* if they are not coplanar. This happens if and only if $\|L \cup \Lambda\| = 4$. Observe that two lines in a projective liner are skew if and only if they are disjoint. A family of lines \mathcal{F} is *skew* if any distinct lines $L, \Lambda \in \mathcal{F}$ are skew.

Given a family of lines \mathcal{F} in a liner X , let \mathcal{F}^\pm be the family of lines which are coplanar with every line in the family $|\mathcal{F}|$. So, $\mathcal{F}^\pm = \{L \in \mathcal{L} : \forall F \in \mathcal{F} (\|F \cup L\| \leq 3)\}$.

Lemma 10.1 ([2, 22.1.1]). *For every skew lines A, B in a weakly modular liner X and every point $x \in \overline{A \cup B}$, there exists a line $L_x \in \{A, B\}^\pm$ such that $x \in L_x$.*

Proposition 10.2 ([2, 22.1.2]). *Let A, B, C be skew lines in a liner X .*

- (1) *If the liner X is 3-ranked, then the family $\{A, B, C\}^\pm$ consists of pairwise disjoint lines.*
- (2) *If the liner X is 4-ranked, then $\bigcup \{A, B, C\}^\pm \subseteq \overline{A \cup B \cap B \cup C \cap A \cup C}$.*
- (3) *If the liner X is weakly modular, then $(A \cap \overline{B \cup C}) \cup (B \cap \overline{A \cup C}) \cup (C \cap \overline{A \cup B}) \subseteq \bigcup \{A, B, C\}^\pm$.*
- (4) *If the liner X is weakly modular and $\|A \cup B \cup C\| = 4$, then $A \cup B \cup C \subseteq \bigcup \{A, B, C\}^\pm \subseteq \overline{A \cup B} = \overline{B \cup C} = \overline{A \cup C} = \overline{A \cup B \cup C}$.*
- (5) *If the liner X is proaffine and regular, then the family $\{A, B, C\}^\pm$ consists of pairwise skew lines.*
- (6) *If the liner X is proaffine and regular and $|\{A, B, C\}^\pm| \geq 2$, then $\|A \cup B \cup C\| = 4$.*

Definition 10.3. A family of lines \mathcal{R} in a liner X is called a *regulus* in X if $|\mathcal{R}| \geq 3$ and $\mathcal{R} = \{A, B, C\}^\pm$ for some skew lines A, B, C in X .

By Proposition 10.2, any regulus $\mathcal{R} = \{A, B, C\}^\pm$ is a proaffine regular liners X consists of skew lines. Given any lines $A', B', C', A'', B'', C'' \in \{A, B, C\}^\pm$ with $|\{A', B', C'\}| = 3 = |\{A'', B'', C''\}|$, we can consider the reguli $\{A', B', C'\}^\pm$ and $\{A'', B'', C''\}^\pm$ and ask when those reguli coincide. This happens for reguli in Gallucci liners, introduced in the next section.

11. GALLUCCI LINERS

In the following definition we identify the number 8 with the set $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ of numbers smaller than 8.

Definition 11.1. A family of eight distinct lines $(L_i)_{i \in 8}$ in a liner X forms a *Gallucci configuration* if for every numbers $i, j \in 8$ with $|i - j| < 7$, the flat $\overline{L_i \cup L_j}$ has rank $\|L_i \cup L_j\| \in |i - j| + 2\mathbb{Z}$. A liner X is called *Gallucci* if for every Gallucci configuration $(L_i)_{i \in 8}$ in X , the lines L_0, L_7 are coplanar.

Observe that two lines L, L' in a liner have

$$\|L \cup L'\| = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{iff } L \text{ and } L' \text{ coincide;} \\ 3 & \text{iff } L \text{ and } L' \text{ are coplanar and distinct;} \\ 4 & \text{iff } L \text{ and } L' \text{ are skew.} \end{cases}$$

So, lines L_i, L_j in a Gallucci configuration $(L_i)_{i \in 8}$ in a Gallucci line are skew if and only if $i - j$ is even.

Theorem 11.2 ([2, 22.2.3]). *Let X be a Gallucci proaffine regular liner. For every regulus \mathcal{R} in X , the family \mathcal{R}^\pm is a regulus in X , equal to the regulus $\{A, B, C\}^\pm$ for every distinct lines $A, B, C \in \mathcal{R}$. Moreover, $\mathcal{R} = (\mathcal{R}^\pm)^\pm$ and $\bigcup \mathcal{R} = \bigcup \mathcal{R}^\pm$.*

Remark 11.3. By Theorem 11.2, for every regulus \mathcal{R} in a Gallucci liner X , the family \mathcal{R}^\pm is a regulus, called to *dual regulus* to the regulus \mathcal{R} . Dual reguli have the same unions.

Example 11.4 ([2, 22.2.5]). For every field F , the families of lines

$$L_a := \{(x, y, z) \in F^3 : z = ax \wedge y = a\} \quad \text{and} \quad \Lambda_b := \{(x, y, z) \in F^3 : x = b \wedge z = by\}$$

determine two dual reguli $\{L_a : a \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}\}$ and $\{\Lambda_b : b \in \mathbb{R}^* \setminus \{0\}\}$ whose unions coincide with the hyperbolic paraboloid $H = \{(x, y, z) \in F^3 : z = xy\}$.

Example 11.5 ([2, 22.2.6]). Let F be a field of characteristic $\neq 2$. The families of lines

$$\begin{aligned} L_a &:= \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : x - z = a(1 - y) \wedge a(x + z) = 1 + y\}, \\ \Lambda_b &:= \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : x + z = b(1 - y) \wedge b(x - z) = 1 + y\} \end{aligned}$$

determine two dual reguli $\{L_a : a \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}\}$ and $\{\Lambda_b : b \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}\}$ whose unions coincide with the one-sheeted hyperboloid $H := \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 : x^2 + y^2 - z^2 = 1\}$ in F^3 .

For projective liners the following theorems were proved by Gallucci [8] in 1906 and reproved by Horváth [15] in 2019.

Theorem 11.6 ([2, 22.3.1]). *Every Pappian proaffine regular liner X is Gallucci.*

Theorem 11.7 ([2, 22.3.3]). *A 3-long proaffine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Gallucci if and only if it is Pappian.*

12. 4-PAPPIAN LINERS

A subset A of a liner X is called *closed* if for any distinct points $a, b, c, d \in A$ with $\overline{ab} \neq \overline{cd}$, we have $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{cd} \subseteq A$. The *closure* $\langle A \rangle$ of a subset A in a liner X is the smallest closed subset of X that contains A . It is equal to the intersection of all closed subsets of X that contain the set A .

Proposition 12.1 ([2, 21.9.1]). *For a liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Pappian;
- (2) for every subset $A \subseteq X$ its closure $\langle A \rangle$ is a Pappian subliner of X .
- (3) for every 5-element subset $A \subseteq X$, its closure $\langle A \rangle$ is a Pappian subliner of X .

Proposition 12.1 motivates the following definition.

Definition 12.2. A liner X is called *4-Pappian* if the closure $\langle A \rangle$ of any 4-element subset A in X is a Pappian subliner of X .

Theorem 12.3 ([2, 45.1.13+45.7.2]). *Any Desarguesian projective liner is 4-Pappian.*

Therefore, for projective liners we have the implications: Pappian \Rightarrow Desarguesian \Rightarrow 4-Pappian.

13. THALESIAN LINERS

Definition 13.1 ([2, 11.1.1]). A liner X is called *Thalesian* if for any plane $P \subseteq X$, pairwise disjoint lines A, B, C in P and any points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the condition $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \emptyset = \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}$ implies $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \emptyset$.

Thalesian 3-ranked liners can be characterized as follows.

Proposition 13.2 ([2, 11.1.2]). *A 3-ranked liner X is Thalesian if and only if for any plane $P \subseteq X$, any distinct parallel lines A, B, C in P and points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, if $\overline{ab} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$ and $\overline{bc} \parallel \overline{b'c'}$, then $\overline{ac} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$.*

Proposition 13.3 ([2, 11.1.3]). *A Proclus liner X is Thalesian if and only if every 3-long plane in X is a Thalesian liner.*

Proposition 13.4 ([2, 11.1.4]). *A proaffine regular liner X is Thalesian if and only if any distinct parallel lines A, B, C and points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the condition $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \emptyset = \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}$ implies $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \emptyset$.*

Theorem 13.5 ([2, 11.1.5]). *Every Desarguesian Proclus liner is Thalesian.*

The following theorem is called the Inverse Thales Theorem.

Theorem 13.6 ([2, 11.1.7]). *Let $abc, a'b'c'$ be two disjoint triangles in a Thalesian para-Playfair liner X such that $\overline{ab} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$, $\overline{bc} \parallel \overline{b'c'}$ and $\overline{ac} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$. If $\overline{aa'} \cap \overline{bb'} = \emptyset$, then $\overline{aa'} \parallel \overline{cc'} \parallel \overline{bb'}$.*

The following example shows that Theorem 13.5 cannot be extended to (pro)affine lines.

Example 13.7 ([2, 11.1.6]). The ring $X := \mathbb{Z}_{15}$ endowed with the family of lines

$$\mathcal{L} = \{L + x : L \in \{\{0, 1, 4\}, \{0, 2, 9\}, \{0, 5, 10\}\}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_{15}\}$$

is a 4-parallel affine balanced Steiner liner, which is Desarguesian, but not Thalesian.

An affine liner X is called *translation* if for any points $x, y \in X$ there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T(x) = y$. We recall that a *translation* of a liner X is any dilation $T : X \rightarrow X$ whose fixed-point set $\text{Fix}(T) := \{x \in X : T(x) = x\}$ equals X or \emptyset .

Theorem 13.8 ([2, 14.4.8]). *An affine space is Thalesian if and only if it is translation.*

Remark 13.9. Theorems 2.1 and 13.5 imply that every proaffine regular liner of rank $\neq 3$ is Desarguesian and hence Thalesian. On the other hand, there are many examples of (finite) Thalesian affine regular planes, which are not Desarguesian, see [16]. Because of the characterization Theorem 13.8, Thalesian Playfair planes are known in the literature as translation affine planes. By Veblen-Wedderburn Theorem 30.3.13 in [2], such planes are isomorphic to affine planes over quasi-fields.

14. THE MOULTON PLANE

The Moulton plane is an example of an affine plane which is not Thalesian (and hence not Desarguesian). The Moulton plane is named after Forest Ray Moulton, american astronomer, who suggested this example in [21].

The Moulton plane is the set $X := \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$ endowed with the family of lines

$$\mathcal{L} := \{L_{a,b} : a, b \in \mathbb{R}\} \cup \{L_c : c \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

where

$$L_{a,b} := \begin{cases} \{(x, ax + b) : x \in \mathbb{R}\} & \text{if } a \geq 0; \\ \{(x, \frac{1}{2}ax + b) : x \leq 0\} \cup \{(x, ax + b) : x \geq 0\} & \text{if } a < 0; \end{cases}$$

and $L_c := \{(c, y) : y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ for real numbers $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}$.

It is easy to check that the Moulton plane is an affine regular liner of rank $\|X\| = 3$. The following picture shows that the Moulton plane is not Thalesian.

The construction of the Moulton plane can be generalized as follows. Take any increasing bijections $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of the real line. The (f, g) -Moulton plane is the plane $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L}_{f,g} := \{L_{a,b} : a, b \in \mathbb{R}\} \cup \{L_c : c \in \mathbb{R}\}$ where

$$L_{a,b} := \begin{cases} \{(x, ax + b) : x \in \mathbb{R}\} & \text{if } a \geq 0; \\ \{(f(x), g(ax + b)) : x \in \mathbb{R}\} & \text{if } a < 0; \end{cases}$$

and $L_c := \{(c, y) : y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ for real numbers $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}$. It can be shown that $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathcal{L}_{f,g})$ is a Playfair plane.

Problem 14.1 ([2, 11.3.4]). *Explore the interplay between the properties of the (f, g) -Moulton plane $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathcal{L}_{f,g})$ and the properties of the increasing bijections f, g .*

15. TWO NON-DESARGUESIAN PLANES OF ORDER 9

In this section we present two examples of non-Desarguesian affine planes of the smallest possible order 9. One of them is Thalesian and the other is not. Both planes are constructed with the help of the near-field \mathbb{J}_9 , defined as follows.

Let $\mathbb{F}_3 = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ be the 3-element field and $\mathbb{J}_9 := \mathbb{F}_3^2$ be the two-dimensional vector space over the field \mathbb{F}_3 . In the vector space \mathbb{J}_9 , consider the vectors $\mathbf{0} := (0, 0)$, $\mathbf{1} := (1, 0)$, $\mathbf{i} := (0, 1)$, $\mathbf{j} := (1, 1)$, $\mathbf{k} := (1, -1)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{J}_9 &= \{(-1, -1), (-1, 0), (-1, 1), (0, -1), (0, 0), (0, 1), (1, -1), (1, 0), (1, 1)\} \\ &= \{-\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{i}, -\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{i}, -\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{i}\} \\ &= \{-\mathbf{j}, -\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{k}, -\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{j}\}\end{aligned}$$

Endow the set \mathbb{J}_9 with the operation of multiplication of quaternion units, which is uniquely determined by the famous Hamilton formula $\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -\mathbf{1}$.

Consider the liner $H := \mathbb{J}_9 \times \mathbb{J}_9$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} := \{L_{a,b} : a, b \in \mathbb{J}_9\} \cup \{L_c : c \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$, where $L_{a,b} = \{(x, xa + b) : x \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$ and $L_c := \{(c, y) : y \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$. It can be shown that the liner H is a Thalesian affine regular liner.

To see that the liner H is not Desarguesian, consider the points $o := (\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0})$, $a := (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{0})$, $b := (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{i})$, $c := (\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{i})$, $a' := (\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{0})$, $b' := (\mathbf{j}, -\mathbf{k})$, $c' := (-\mathbf{k}, -\mathbf{k})$. It can be shown that $\overline{aa'} = \overline{ob} = \overline{oc} = L_{\mathbf{0},\mathbf{0}}$, $\overline{bb'} = \overline{ob} = \overline{ob'} = L_{\mathbf{i},\mathbf{0}}$, $\overline{cc'} = \overline{oc} = \overline{oc'} = L_{\mathbf{1},\mathbf{0}}$, which implies that the triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ are perspective from the point $o := (\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0})$. On the other hand, $\overline{ab} = L_{\mathbf{1}} \parallel L_{\mathbf{j}} = \overline{a'b'}$, $\overline{bc} = L_{\mathbf{0},\mathbf{i}} \parallel L_{\mathbf{0},-\mathbf{k}} = \overline{b'c'}$ and $\overline{ac} = L_{\mathbf{j},-\mathbf{j}}$, $\overline{a'c'} = L_{-\mathbf{k},\mathbf{i}}$, and which implies that $\overline{ac} \not\parallel \overline{a'c'}$ and witnesses that the affine liner H is not Desarguesian.

This Thalesian affine plane H has a dual plane H' , which is not Thalesian. This dual plane H' is the set $\mathbb{J}_9 \times \mathbb{J}_9$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L}' := \{L'_{a,b} : a, b \in \mathbb{J}_9\} \cup \{L'_c : c \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$, where $L'_{a,b} := \{ax + b : x \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$ and $L'_c := \{(c, y) : y \in \mathbb{J}_9\}$. It can be shown that the liner $H' := (\mathbb{J}_9 \times \mathbb{J}_9, \mathcal{L}')$ is affine and regular. To see that the affine liner H' is not Thalesian, consider the points $a := (\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$, $b := (\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0})$, $c := (\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{i})$, and $a' := (\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{1})$, $b' := (\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{0})$, $c' := (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{i})$, and observe that $\overline{aa'} = L'_{\mathbf{0},\mathbf{1}}$, $\overline{bb'} = L'_{\mathbf{0},\mathbf{0}}$, $\overline{cc'} = L'_{\mathbf{0},\mathbf{i}}$, which implies that the lines $\overline{aa'}$, $\overline{bb'}$, $\overline{cc'}$ are parallel. Also $\overline{ab} = L'_{\mathbf{0}} \parallel L'_{\mathbf{1}} = \overline{a'b'}$ and $\overline{bc} = L'_{\mathbf{1},\mathbf{0}} \parallel L'_{\mathbf{1},-\mathbf{k}} = \overline{b'c'}$ and $\overline{ac} = L'_{\mathbf{j},\mathbf{1}}$, $\overline{a'c'} = L'_{-\mathbf{i},-\mathbf{i}}$, and hence $\overline{ac} \not\parallel \overline{a'c'}$, witnessing that the affine liner H' is not Thalesian.

The spread completions of the non-Desarguesian planes H' and H are called the *Hall projective plane* and the *dual Hall projective plane* of order 9, respectively. Besides those two non-Desarguesian projective planes, there is another non-Desarguesian plane of order 9 called the *Hughes plane*. All three non-Desarguesian planes of order 9 were known to Veblen and Weddenburn [28] already in 1907. Only in 1991, by a computer search, Lam, Kolesova and Thiel [18] proved that there are exactly four non-isomorphic projective planes of order 9: *desarg*, *hall*, *dhall*, and *hughes*. Removing suitable lines from those four projective planes of order 9, we obtain seven (pairwise non-isomorphic) affine planes of order 9: *Desarg*, *Hall*, *hall*, *Thales*, *dhall*, *Hughes*, and *hughes*. The automorphism groups of those seven affine planes have the following orders.

Affine plane Π :	Desarg	Thales	Hall	hall	dhall	Hughes	hughes
$ \text{Aut}(\Pi) $:	933120	311040	311040	3840	3456	2592	432

16. MOUFANG LINERS

In this section we introduce Moufang liners, called in honour of Ruth Moufang (1905–1977), a famous German mathematician who deeply studied such liners and proved that Playfair (or projective) Moufang planes are isomorphic to (projective completions of) coordinate planes of alternative rings.

Definition 16.1. A liner X is called *Moufang* if for any disjoint centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ with $b' \in \overline{ac}$, the set $(\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2.

Proposition 16.2 ([2, 10.6.5]). *Every Desarguesian liner is Moufang.*

Proposition 16.3 ([2, 10.6.3]). *A liner X is Moufang if and only if every plane in X is Moufang.*

For Proclus liners, Proposition 16.3 can be improved as follows.

Proposition 16.4 ([2, 10.6.4]). *A Proclus liner X is Moufang if and only if every 3-long plane in X is Moufang.*

Proposition 16.5 ([2, 10.6.6]). *For every flat H in a Moufang projective liner Y , the subliner $X := Y \setminus H$ of Y is Moufang.*

Proposition 16.6 ([2, 10.6.7]). *Let Y be a projective completion of a 3-long liner X . If X is Moufang, then the horizon $Y \setminus X$ of X in Y is flat and hence the liner X is completely regular.*

Theorem 16.7 ([2, 10.6.8]). *Every Moufang proaffine regular liner X is completely regular.*

17. LITTLE-DESARGUESIAN LINERS

Definition 17.1. A liner X is called *little-Desarguesian* if for any distinct lines $A, B, C, D \subset X$ and distinct points $o \in A \cap B \cap C \cap D$, $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the condition $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} \cap D \neq \emptyset \neq \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} \cap D$ implies $D \cap \overline{ac} \subseteq \overline{a'c'}$.

The following two characterizations of little-Desarguesian liners are counterparts of Propositions 16.3 and 16.4 characterizing Moufang liners.

Proposition 17.2 ([2, 44.1.2]). *A liner X is little-Desarguesian if and only if every plane in X is little-Desarguesian.*

For Proclus liners, Proposition 17.2 can be improved as follows.

Proposition 17.3 ([2, 44.1.3]). *A Proclus liner X is little-Desarguesian if and only if every 3-long plane in X is little-Desarguesian.*

Proposition 17.4 ([2, 44.1.4]). *Every Moufang liner is little-Desarguesian.*

Theorem 17.5 ([2, 44.2.1]). *A projective completion of any little-Desarguesian liner is Moufang.*

Corollary 17.6 ([2, 44.1.10]). *Every Steiner 3-regular liner is Moufang and little-Desarguesian.*

Proposition 17.7 ([2, 44.1.6]). *Any subliner X of a little-Desarguesian liner Y is little-Desarguesian.*

Corollary 17.8 ([2, 44.1.7]). *A liner is little-Desarguesian if it has a little-Desarguesian projective completion.*

Therefore, for any liner we have the implications: Desarguesian \Rightarrow Moufang \Rightarrow little-Desarguesian. None of those implications can be reversed.

Example 17.9 (Moufang, 1931). The octonion plane $\mathbb{O} \times \mathbb{O}$ is a Playfair plane, which is Moufang but not Desarguesian.

Example 17.10 ([2, 44.1.9]). Take any 4-long Moufang projective plane Y and choose any line $L \subset Y$ and point $p \in L$. The subliner $X := Y \setminus (L \setminus \{p\})$ is Proclus and little-Desarguesian, but not Moufang.

Example 17.11 ([2, 44.1.11]). The cyclic group $\mathbb{Z}_{25} = \{0, 1, \dots, 24\}$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} := \{L + x : L \in \{\{0, 1, 12\}, \{0, 2, 18\}, \{0, 3, 8\}, \{0, 4, 19\}\}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_{25}\}$ is a Steiner ranked plane, which is not little-Desarguesian.

18. MOUFANG PROJECTIVE SPACES

The following important theorem characterizes Moufang projective spaces.

Theorem 18.1 ([2, 44.3.1]). *For any projective space, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) Y is Moufang;
- (2) Y is little-Desarguesian;
- (3) every subliner of X is little-Desarguesian;
- (4) for some set $H \subseteq Y$ with $\bar{H} \neq Y$, the subliner $Y \setminus H$ is little-Desarguesian;
- (5) for every flat set H in Y , the subliner $Y \setminus H$ is Moufang;
- (6) for every hyperplane H in Y , the subliner $Y \setminus H$ is Moufang;
- (7) for every hyperplane H in Y , the subliner $Y \setminus H$ is Thalesian;
- (8) for two distinct hyperplanes H, H' in Y , the liners $Y \setminus H$ and $Y \setminus H'$ are Thalesian.

Let us recall that a projective liner Y is *somewhere \mathcal{P}* (resp. *everywhere \mathcal{P}*) if for some (resp. every) hyperplane $H \subseteq Y$, the affine subliner $Y \setminus H$ of Y has property \mathcal{P} .

Theorem 18.1 implies the following characterization of Moufang projective spaces in terms of somewhere/everywhere \mathcal{P} properties.

Corollary 18.2 ([2, 44.3.3]). *For a projective space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Moufang;
- (2) X is somewhere Moufang;
- (3) X is everywhere Moufang;
- (4) X is little-Desarguesian;
- (5) X is somewhere little-Desarguesian;
- (6) X is everywhere little-Desarguesian;
- (7) X is everywhere Thalesian.

19. COMPLETELY REGULAR MOUFANG LINERS

Theorem 19.1 ([2, 44.4.1]). *For a completely regular liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Moufang;
- (2) X is little-Desarguesian;
- (3) the spread completion of X is Moufang;
- (4) some projective completion of X is Moufang.

Let us recall that a property \mathcal{P} of liners is called *complete* if a completely regular liner has property \mathcal{P} if and only if its spread completion has property \mathcal{P} . A liner X is *completely \mathcal{P}* for some property \mathcal{P} of projective liners if X is completely regular and its spread completion \bar{X} has property \mathcal{P} . Theorem 19.1 implies the following important facts.

Corollary 19.2 ([2, 41.4.2]). *The properties of a liner to be Moufang (resp. little-Desarguesian) are complete.*

Corollary 19.3 ([2, 44.4.3]). *For a 3-long liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is regular and Moufang;
- (2) X is completely regular and little-Desarguesian;
- (3) X is 3-ranked and the spread completion of X is Moufang and projective;
- (4) X has a Moufang projective completion with flat horizon.

- (5) X is completely little-Desarguesian;
- (6) X is completely Moufang.

20. PARA-DESARGUESIAN LINERS

In this section we introduce para-Desarguesian liners satisfying a “parallel” version of the Desargues Axiom and establish some basic property of such liners.

Definition 20.1. A liner X is called *para-Desarguesian* if for any plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, disjoint lines $A, B, C, D \subseteq \Pi$, and distinct points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the condition $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} \cap D \neq \emptyset \neq \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} \cap D$ implies $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} \subseteq D$.

Definition 20.1 implies the following simple (but useful) characterization of para-Desarguesian liners.

Proposition 20.2 ([2, 44.5.1]). *A liner X is para-Desarguesian if and only if every plane in X is para-Desarguesian.*

Many examples of para-Desarguesian liners can be constructed using the following proposition.

Proposition 20.3 ([2, 44.5.3]). *Any proaffine subliner of a projective Moufang liner is para-Desarguesian.*

Example 20.4 ([2, 44.5.4]). The complement $X := Y \setminus (L \setminus \{p\})$ to a line L with removed point p in a 4-long Moufang projective liner Y of rank $\|Y\| \geq 4$ is an example of a para-Desarguesian liner, which is not regular, not para-Playfair, and not Moufang.

Proposition 20.5 ([2, 44.5.5]). *Every Moufang Proclus liner is para-Desarguesian.*

Corollary 20.6 ([2, 44.5.6]). *Every Steiner 3-regular liner is para-Desarguesian.*

The 3-regularity in Corollary 20.6 is essential as shows the following example.

Example 20.7 ([2, 44.5.7]). The cyclic group $\mathbb{Z}_{15} = \{0, 1, \dots, 15\}$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} = \{L + x : L \in \{\{0, 1, 4\}, \{0, 2, 9\}, \{0, 5, 10\}\}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_{15}\}$ is an affine Steiner ranked plane, which is Desarguesian and Moufang, but not Thalesian and not para-Desarguesian.

21. PARA-DESARGUESIAN PARA-PLAYFAIR LINERS

In this section we study the interplay between the para-Desarguesian and para-Playfair liners.

Proposition 21.1 ([2, 44.6.1]). *Let X be a para-Desarguesian para-Playfair liner. For any plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, disjoint lines $A, B, C, D \subseteq \Pi$ and distinct points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, if $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} \cap D \neq \emptyset \neq \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'} \cap D$ then $\emptyset \neq \overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} \subseteq D$.*

A liner X is called *shear* if for any hyperplane H in X and distinct points $a, a' \in X$ with $\overline{xy} \cap H = \emptyset$, there exists an automorphism Φ of X such that $\Phi(a) = a'$ and the fixed point set $\text{Fix}(\Phi) := \{z \in X : \Phi(z) = z\}$ of Φ equals H .

Proposition 21.2 ([2, 44.6.2]). *Every shear Proclus plane is para-Desarguesian.*

The following important theorem was first proved by Oleksiï Ilchuk in his Bachelor Thesis [17].

Theorem 21.3 ([2, 44.6.6]). *A para-Playfair plane is para-Desarguesian if and only if it is shear.*

Theorem 21.4 ([2, 44.6.9]). *A para-Desarguesian liner is completely regular if and only if it is regular and para-Playfair.*

Corollary 21.5 ([2, 44.6.11]). *A 4-long para-Desarguesian liner is completely regular if and only if it is para-Playfair.*

Corollary 21.6 ([2, 44.6.12]). *Every para-Desarguesian para-Playfair liner X is Thalesian.*

Example 21.7 ([2, 44.6.13]). The cyclic group $\mathbb{Z}_{13} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 12\}$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} := \{x + \{0, 3, 4\}, x + \{0, 5, 7\} : x \in \mathbb{Z}_{13}\}$ is an example of a non-regular para-Desarguesian Steiner (and hence proaffine) ranked plane, which is not Thalesian.

A liner X is called *hypersymmetric* if for any triangle abc in X there exists an involutive automorphism A of X such that $Aabc = cba$ and the fixed-point set $\text{Fix}(A) := \{x \in X : A(x) = x\}$ of A contains some hyperplane of X .

Theorem 21.8 ([2, 44.7.1]). *For any affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Moufang;
- (2) X is little-Desarguesian;
- (3) X is para-Desarguesian;
- (4) X is shear;
- (5) X is hypersymmetric;
- (6) the spread completion of X is Moufang.

The following non-trivial theorem is deduced from the famous Artin–Zorn Theorem [2, 30.3.3] (saying that every finite alternative divisible ring is a field).

Theorem 21.9 ([2, 44.8.1]). *A finite Proclus liner is Moufang if and only if it is Desarguesian if and only if it is Pappian.*

22. HOMOGENEITY OF MOUFANG LINERS

A *quadrangle* in a liner X is a quadruple $abcd$ of distinct points $a, b, c, d \in X$ such that $\|\{x, y, z\}\| = 3 = \|\{a, b, c, d\}\|$ for any distinct points $x, y, z \in \{a, b, c, d\}$. A quadrangle $abcd$ in a liner X is called *complete* if the set $D := (\overline{a b} \cap \overline{c d}) \cup (\overline{b c} \cap \overline{a d}) \cup (\overline{a c} \cap \overline{b d})$ has cardinality $|D| = 3$. It is easy to see that every quadrangle in a projective liner is complete.

Definition 22.1. A liner X is defined to be

- *1-homogeneous* if for any points $a, b \in X$ there exists an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ such that $\Phi(a) = b$;
- *2-homogeneous* if for any doubletons¹ $ab, a'b'$ in X , there exists an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ such that $(\Phi(a), \Phi(b)) = (a', b')$;
- *3-homogeneous* if for any triangles $abc, a'b'c'$ in X , there exists an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ such that $(\Phi(a), \Phi(b), \Phi(c)) = (a', b', c')$;
- *4-homogeneous* if for any quadrangles $abcd, a'b'c'd'$ in X , there exists an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ such that $(\Phi(a), \Phi(b), \Phi(c), \Phi(d)) = (a', b', c', d')$.

The following theorem on 3-homogeneity of Moufang projective planes was proved by Marshal Hall in [10].

Theorem 22.2 ([2, 44.9.2]). *Every 3-long Moufang projective plane is 3-homogeneous.*

The following difficult theorem on the 4-homogeneity of non-Fano Moufang projective planes was proved by Bruck and Kleinfeld in [5].

Theorem 22.3 ([2, 44.9.3]). *Any 3-long non-Fano Moufang projective plane is 4-homogeneous.*

Corollary 22.4 ([2, 44.9.5]). *Any non-Fano Moufang affine space is 3-homogeneous.*

¹A *doubleton* is an ordered pair ab of distinct points.

Remark 22.5. Theorem and Corollary 22.4 cannot be reversed: in Corollary 2.3 of [19], Kegel and Schleiermacher constructed an infinite 4-homogeneous projective plane P which is not Moufang (more precisely, every quadrangle $abcd$ in P generates a closed subliner of P , isomorphic to the free projectivization of the subliner $\{a, b, c, d\}$ of P). Removing any line from the Kegel–Schleiermacher projective plane P , we obtain a 3-homogeneous affine plane, which is not Moufang.

Problem 22.6. *Is every Fano Moufang projective space 4-homogeneous? Is every Fano affine space 3-homogeneous?*

On the other hand, for finite projective planes, Ostrom and Wagner [23] proved the following homogeneity result.

Theorem 22.7 (Ostrom, Wagner, 1959). *Every 2-homogeneous finite projective plane is Desarguesian.*

An affine counterpart of Theorem 22.7 was proved by Jha and Jonson in 1998.

Theorem 22.8 (Jha, Johnson, 1998). *Every 2-homogeneous finite affine plane X is Thalesian. If $|X|_2 \notin \{9, 27\}$, then the affine plane X is Desarguesian.*

Remark 22.9. The exceptional non-Desarguesian 2-transitive affine planes of orders 9 and 27 are the Thalesian plane $X = \mathbb{J}_9 \times \mathbb{J}_9$, described in Section 15, and the *Herring plane*, discovered by Christoph Hering [22] in 1970. Computer calculations show that those two exceptional planes are not 3-transitive, so, we have the following homogeneity result for finite affine planes.

Corollary 22.10 ([2, 44.9.13]). *Every 3-homogeneous finite affine plane X is Desarguesian.*

23. FANO LINERS

Definition 23.1. A liner X is *Fano* if for any distinct points $a, b, c, d \in \Pi$, the set

$$D := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{cd}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{ad}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{bd})$$

has rank $\|D\| \in \{0, 2\}$.

Fano liners can be equivalently defined by requiring all quadrangles to be Fano.

Definition 23.2. A quadrangle $abcd$ in a liner is defined to be *Fano* if the set

$$D := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{cd}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{ad}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{bd})$$

has rank $\|D\| \in \{0, 2\}$.

Proposition 23.3 ([2, 43.1.5]). *A liner X is Fano if and only if every quadrangle in X is Fano.*

Example 23.4 ([2, 43.1.6]). Every Steiner projective liner X is Fano.

For projective liners, the following important theorem was proved by Gleason [9] in 1956.

Theorem 23.5 ([2, 43.4.1]). *Every finite proaffine Fano liner is Pappian.*

Problem 23.6 ([2, 50.4.2]). *Is every Fano projective plane Moufang?*

24. BOOLEAN LINERS

Definition 24.1. A liner X is *Boolean* if for any distinct points $a, b, c, d \in X$ with $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{cd} = \emptyset = \overline{bc} \cap \overline{ad}$ we have $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{bd} = \emptyset$.

Proposition 24.2 ([2, 43.1.7]). *Every Fano liner is Boolean.*

Remark 24.3 ([2, 43.1.8]). Proposition 24.2 cannot be reversed: any non-Pappian Thalesian Playfair liner of order $2^n \geq 16$ is Boolean but not Fano.

Proposition 24.4 ([2, 43.1.11]). *A Thalesian affine space X is Boolean if and only if it contains a Boolean parallelogram.*

Problem 24.5 ([2, 50.2.1]). *Is every (finite) Boolean Playfair plane Thalesian?*

The following theorem shows that a projective liner is Fano if and only if it is everywhere Boolean.

Theorem 24.6 ([2, 43.1.9+43.1.10]). *For any projective liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Fano;
- (2) for every flat H in X , the subliner $X \setminus H$ of X is Fano;
- (3) for every flat H in X , the subliner $X \setminus H$ of X is Boolean;
- (4) for every hyperplane H in X , the subliner $X \setminus H$ of X is Boolean.

If the projective liner X is 4-long and Moufang, then the conditions (1)–(4) are equivalent to each of the conditions:

- (5) for some hyperplane H in X , the subliner $X \setminus H$ of X is Boolean;
- (6) for some hyperplane H in X , the affine subliner $X \setminus H$ of X contains a Boolean parallelogram.

25. REGULARITY OF PROAFFINE FANO LINERS

The main result of this section is the following theorem on the 3-regularity of proaffine Fano liners.

Theorem 25.1 ([2, 43.2.5]). *Every proaffine Fano liner X is 3-regular.*

Example 25.2 ([2, 43.2.7]). For any Steiner projective liner X of rank $\|X\| = 4$ and any line L in X the Fano subliner $X \setminus L$ of X is 3-regular but not regular.

Corollary 25.3 ([2, 43.2.6]). *Every proaffine Fano liner X is Proclus and para-Playfair.*

Proposition 25.4 ([2, 43.2.8]). *Every Boolean para-Playfair regular liner X is completely regular.*

Theorem 25.5 ([2, 43.2.9]). *Every weakly regular proaffine Fano liner X is completely regular.*

Corollary 25.6 ([2, 43.2.10]). *Every proaffine Fano liner X of rank $\|X\| = 3$ is completely regular.*

Example 25.7 ([2, 43.2.11]). Let Y be a Steiner projective liner of rank $\|X\| = 4$. For every line $L \subset Y$, the subliner $X := Y \setminus L$ is proaffine and Fano, but not regular. This example shows that Corollary 25.6 cannot be extended to arbitrary proaffine Fano liners. On the other hand, by Theorem 26.4, every *finite* 3-long proaffine Fano liner is completely regular.

Problem 25.8. *Is every ω -long proaffine Fano liner regular?*

26. THE SPREAD COMPLETIONS OF FANO LINERS

In section we explore the structure of the spread completions of completely regular Fano liners. The following completion theorem was first proved by Oksana Skyhar in her Bachelor Thesis [27].

Theorem 26.1 ([2, 43.3.1]). *The spread completion of any proaffine Fano plane is a projective Fano plane.*

Corollary 26.2 ([2, 43.3.2]). *Every Steiner Fano liner is projective.*

Theorem 26.3 ([2, 43.3.3]). *The spread completion of any completely regular Fano liner is a projective Fano liner.*

The following theorem characterizes completely regular 3-long Fano liners.

Theorem 26.4 ([2, 43.3.4]). *For a 3-long liner X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Fano, proaffine, and weakly regular;
- (2) X is Fano and completely regular;
- (3) X is completely regular and its spread completion is Fano;
- (4) X is 3-ranked and its spread completion is a Fano projective liner;
- (5) X has a Fano projective completion with flat horizon;
- (6) X is Fano and has a projective completion;

(7) X is Fano, proaffine, and regular.

If the liner X is finite, then (1)–(7) are equivalent to the condition

(8) X is proaffine and Fano.

By Theorem 24.6, a 3-long projective liner is Fano if and only if it is everywhere Fano if and only if it is everywhere Boolean. The following corollary implies that a 3-long projective liner is Fano if and only if it is somewhere Fano.

Corollary 26.5 ([2, 43.3.5]). *For a 3-long projective liner Y , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) Y is Fano;
- (2) for every flat H in Y , the liner $Y \setminus H$ is Fano;
- (3) for every hyperplane H in Y , the liner $Y \setminus H$ is Boolean;
- (4) for some hyperplane H in Y , the liner $Y \setminus H$ is Fano;
- (5) for some proper flat H in Y , the liner $Y \setminus H$ is Fano;
- (6) Y is a projective completion of some affine regular Fano liner;
- (7) Y is a projective completion of some proaffine Fano liner.

Let us recall that a liner X is *completely* \mathcal{P} for some property \mathcal{P} of projective liners if X is completely regular and its spread completion \overline{X} has property \mathcal{P} .

Corollary 26.6 ([2, 43.3.6]). *A liner is completely Fano if and only if it is Fano, proaffine, and (weakly) regular.*

27. MORE INCIDENCES IN THE DESARGUES AXIOM

In this section we consider some weaker versions of the Desargues Axiom with some additional incidences. Two triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in a liner are called *coplanar* if the points a, b, c, a', b', c' belong to some plane. In the following definition we label by (D) the Desargues Axiom and then formulate its weakenings.

Definition 27.1. A liner X is called

- (D) *Desarguesian* if for any centrally perspective coplanar disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X , the set $(\overline{ab \cap a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc \cap b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac \cap a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2;
- (D_I) *uno-Desarguesian* if for any centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X with $b' \in \overline{ac}$, the set $(\overline{ab \cap a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc \cap b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac \cap a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2;
- (D_{II}) *duo-Desarguesian* if for any centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X with $a' \in \overline{bc}$ and $c' \in \overline{ab}$, the set $(\overline{ab \cap a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc \cap b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac \cap a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2;
- (D_{III}) *bi-Desarguesian* if for any centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X with $b' \in \overline{ac}$ and $b \in \overline{a'c'}$, the set $(\overline{ab \cap a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc \cap b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac \cap a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2;
- (D_{IV}) *tri-Desarguesian* if for any centrally perspective disjoint triangles abc and $a'b'c'$ in X with $a' \in \overline{bc}$, $b' \in \overline{ac}$, $c' \in \overline{ab}$, the set $(\overline{ab \cap a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc \cap b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac \cap a'c'})$ has rank 0 or 2.

By Definitions 27.1 and 16.1, a liner is uno-Desarguesian if and only if it is Moufang. The following two theorems are less trivial.

Theorem 27.2 ([2, 46.1.2]). *For any projective space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is duo-Desarguesian;
- (2) X is bi-Desarguesian;
- (3) X is Fano or Moufang.

The following characterization is a classical result of Ruth Moufang [20].

Theorem 27.3 (Moufang; [2, 46.1.3]). *A projective liner is tri-Desarguesian iff it is 4-Pappian.*

Therefore, we obtain the following diagram holding for every projective space.

This diagram motivates the following (known) open problems.

Problem 27.4 ([2, 50.8.9]). *Is every 4-Pappian projective plane Fano or Moufang?*

Problem 27.5 ([2, 50.2.4]). *Is every Fano projective plane Moufang?*

28. MORE INCIDENCES IN THE PAPPUS AXIOM

In this section we consider eight weaker modifications of the Pappus Axiom (P), defined as follows.

Definition 28.1. For a liner X , consider the following weaker modifications of the Pappus Axiom:

- (P) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, the set $T := (\overline{a b' \cap a' b}) \cup (\overline{b c' \cap b' c}) \cup (\overline{a c' \cap a' c})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- (P₉⁹) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₉¹⁰) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c}$, $o \in L \cap L' \cap \overline{a b}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₁₀⁹) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c} \cap \overline{b b'}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₁₀¹⁰) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c} \cap \overline{b b'}$, $o \in L \cap L' \cap \overline{a x z}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₁₂¹⁰) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c}$, $w \in \overline{a a' \cap b b' \cap c c'}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₁₀¹²) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c}$, $u \in \overline{a b' \cap b c'}$, $v \in \overline{a' b \cap b' c}$, $o \in L \cap L' \cap \overline{u v}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P₁₃¹³) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c}$, $u \in \overline{a b' \cap b c'}$, $v \in \overline{a' b \cap b' c}$, $o \in L \cap L' \cap \overline{u v}$, $w \in \overline{a a' \cap b b' \cap c c'}$, the points x, y, z are collinear;
- (P̄₁₃¹³) for every lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, $x \in \overline{a b' \cap a' b}$, $y \in \overline{b c' \cap b' c}$, $z \in \overline{a c' \cap a' c} \cap \overline{b b'}$, $u \in \overline{a b' \cap b c'}$, $v \in \overline{a' b \cap b' c}$, $w \in \overline{a a' \cap b b' \cap c c'}$, $o \in L \cap L' \cap \overline{u v}$, the points x, y, z are collinear.

For a pair of numbers $(n, m) \in \{(9, 9), (9, 10), (10, 9), (10, 12), (12, 10), (13, 13)\}$, a liner X is defined to be (P_n^m) if it satisfies the axiom (P_n^m).

Remark 28.2. The notations of the axioms (P_n^m) in Definition 28.1 have upper and lower indices corresponding to the number of points and lines involved in the definition of the axiom. The axioms (P₁₃¹³) and (P̄₁₃¹³) both involve 13 points and 13 lines, but (P̄₁₃¹³) has two incidences more comparing to the axiom (P₁₃¹³). In [1], the axioms (P₁₀⁹) and (P₉¹⁰) are denoted by (P₁) and (P₂), and called the First and the Second Minor Pappus Axioms, respectively. Pickert [24] calls these axioms the Axial and the Central Pappus Axioms, respectively. In [1], the axioms (P₁₂¹⁰), (P₁₀¹²) are denoted by (P₃), (P₄), and called the Third and the Forth Minor Pappus Axioms, respectively.

Theorem 28.3 ([2, §46.2]). *Let X be a 3-long projective liner.*

- (1) X is (P₉⁹) if and only if X is Pappian.
- (2) X is (P₁₀⁹) and (P₉¹⁰) if and only if X Fano or Moufang.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.W. Al-Dhahir, K. Ghalieh, *On minor forms of Desargues and Pappus*, Geom. Dedicata **42**:3 (1992), 329–344.
- [2] T. Banakh, *Linear Geometry and Algebra*, (2025); <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.14060>.
- [3] T. Banakh, I. Hetman, V. Pshyk, A. Ravsky, *Linear Geomery: flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity*, Mat. Studii, **65**:1 (2026), 74–96.
- [4] T. Banakh, I. Hetman, V. Pshyk, A. Ravsky, *Linear Geomery: completions and projectivizations*, preprint (2025); (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17920429>).
- [5] R.H. Bruck, E. Kleinfeld, *The structure of alternative division rings*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. **2** (1951), 878–890
- [6] A. Cronheim, *A proof of Hessenberg’s theorem*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. **4** (1953), 219–221.
- [7] R.H. Bruck, H.J. Ryser, *The nonexistence of certain finite projective planes*, Canad. J. Math. **1** (1949), 88–93.
- [8] G. Gallucci, *Studio della figura delle otto rette e sue applicazioni alla geometria del tetraedro ed alla teoria della configurazioni*, Rendiconto dell’ Accademia della Scienze Fisiche e Matematiche. **12**:3 (1906) 49–79.
- [9] A.M. Gleason, *Finite Fano planes*, Amer. J. Math. **78** (1956), 797–807.
- [10] M. Hall, *Projective planes*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **54** (1943), 229–277.
- [11] M. Hall Jr., *Uniqueness of the projective plane with 57 points*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. **4** (1953), 912–916.
- [12] M. Hall Jr, *Correction to “Uniqueness of the projective plane with 57 points”*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. **5** (1954), 994–997.
- [13] M. Hall Jr., J.D. Swift, R.J. Walker, *Uniqueness of the projective plane of order eight*, Math. Tables Aids Comput. **10** (1956), 186–194.
- [14] G. Hessenberg, *Beweis des Desarguesschen Satzes aus dem Pascalschen*, Mathematische Annalen, **61**:2 (1905), 161–172.
- [15] A.G. Horváth, *The theorem of Gallucci revisited*, Journal for Geometry and Graphics. **23**:2 (2019), 167–178.
- [16] N.L. Johnson, V. Jha, M. Biliotti, *Handbook of finite translation planes*, Pure and Applied Mathematics (Boca Raton), 289. Chapman & Hall/CRC, Boca Raton, FL, 2007. xxii+861 pp.
- [17] O. Ilchuk, *Moufang liners*, Bachelor Thesis, Lviv, 2025.
- [18] C.W. Lam, G. Kolesova, L. Thiel, *A computer search for finite projective planes of order 9*, Discrete Math. **92**:1–3 (1991), 187–195.
- [19] O. Kegel, A. Schleiermacher, *Amalgams and embeddings of projective planes*, Geometriae Dedicata **2** (1973), 379–395.
- [20] R. Moufang, *Zur Struktur der projektiven Ebenen*, Mathematische Annalen **105** (1931), 536–601.
- [21] F.R. Moulton, *A simple non-Desarguesian plane geometry*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **3**:2 (1902), 192–195.
- [22] C. Hering, *Eine nicht-desarguessche zweifach transitive affine Ebene der Ordnung 27*, Abh. Math. Sem. Univ. Hamburg **34** (1970), 203–208.
- [23] T.G. Ostrom, A. Wagner, *On projective and affine planes with transitive collineation groups*, Math. Z. **71** (1959), 186–199.
- [24] G. Pickert, *Projektive Ebenen*, Die Grundlehren der mathematischen Wissenschaften, Band 80. Springer-Verlag, Berlin-New York, 1975. ix+371 pp
- [25] M. Prażmowska, *A proof of the projective Desargues axiom in the Desarguesian affine plane*, Demonstratio Math. **37**:4 (2004), 921–924.
- [26] V. Pshyk, *On Pappian and Desarguesian affine planes*, Mat. Studii. **64**:1 (2025), 92–98.
- [27] O. Skyhar, *Fano liners*, Bachelor Thesis, Lviv, 2025.
- [28] O. Veblen, J.H. Maclagan-Wedderburn, *Non-Desarguesian and non-Pascalian geometries*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **8**:3 (1907), 379–388.

T. BANAKH: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
 AND JAN KOCHANOWSKI UNIVERSITY IN KIELCE (POLAND)
 Email address: t.o.banakh@gmail.com

I. HETMAN: LVIV (UKRAINE)
 Email address: vespertilion@gmail.com

O. ILCHUK: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
 Email address: alexilchuk4@gmail.com

V. PSHYK: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
 Email address: pshik.vlad8@gmail.com
 Email address: vitaravski@gmail.com

O. SKYHAR: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
 Email address: oksana.skyhar@lnu.edu.ua